

The Concept of Critical Increment and Radiation Hypothesis.

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It is well known that the variation of velocity constant of chemical reaction with temperature is given by the relation

$$\frac{d \log k}{dT} = \frac{E}{RT^2}$$

where E is the so-called critical increment in energy which activates a molecule.

The radiation hypothesis for explaining this equation proceeds from the Planck equation,

$$\frac{\text{Probability of no emission by oscillator}}{\text{Probability of emission by oscillator}} = 1/e^{\frac{h\nu}{kT} - 1}$$

and assumes that this expression also gives the ratio

$$\frac{\text{No. of active molecules.}}{\text{No. of inactive molecules}}$$

$$\text{Hence, } \frac{\text{No. of active molecules}}{\text{Total No. of molecules}} = e^{-h\nu/kT} = e^{-Nh\nu/RT}$$

if E is identified with $Nh\nu$.

The term E , represents critical increment, before a molecule becomes active. It is possible to conceive that a molecule retains its absorbed energy, but the energy is not sufficient to bring it to critical state. In this case we cannot identify the active state with the state of energy retention. Secondly, a molecule may lose its energy that has been absorbed, and still possess an energy greater than the critical. In this case again we fail to identify the two states of energy emission and inactive condition. It will be clear, therefore, that the above assumption introduced in deducing $E \equiv Nh\nu$ is doubtful. Really the equation

$$\frac{d \log k}{dt} = \frac{Nh\nu}{RT^2}$$

does not represent the variation of the velocity constant with temperature, and k , is not really the velocity constant of the chemical reaction, but represents the variation in the number of molecules which are capable of retaining the absorbed energy of the frequency ν , with temperature. It follows, therefore, that this k is not necessarily identical with the k of Marcelin and Rice's equation which corresponds to velocity constant of the reaction and hence we are not justified in putting $R = Nh\nu$.

Consequences of our failure in identifying the active and energy retention state are obvious. Since $E \neq Nh\nu$

(1) The ν , so calculated on the basis of identity between two states need not be absorbed by the reacting system.

(2) The radiation may be absorbed but it fails to accelerate the reaction, since the process of energy retention need not necessarily increase the energy to critical state.

These conclusions are in accordance with the experimental observations. We find that the Radiation hypothesis fails in two ways:

(i) The calculated wave-length from $E = Nh\nu$ is not absorbed by the reacting system.

(ii) The absorbed wave-length fails to accelerate the reaction.

These two ways of failure are identical according to my conclusion. It is clear, therefore, that this deviation is mainly due to the reason mentioned above.

Thus according to Daniels and Johnston (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 53) there is no acceleration of the reaction for nitrogen pentoxide by the radiation of wave-length 11600 Å which is obtained from temperature coefficient. Similar results were obtained by Daniels (*ibid.*, 1927, **49**, 617) in case of N_2O_5 ; by Urey and Tolman (*ibid.*, 1929, **51**, 974) for the velocity of recombination of *d*-pinene in liquid state; by Fromageot (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1927, *iv*, **41**, 1585) in the reduction of ceric salts by acetaldehyde and by Hibben (*Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1927, **13**, 626; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **50**, 937, 940) for the decomposition of nitrous oxide when exposed to infra-red radiations. All these deviations, therefore, can be explained from view point of the present author.

However, when there is identity between active state and the state of energy retention for a molecule, then $E = Nh\nu$ and hence the value of ν calculated from temperature coefficient should be absorbed by the reacting system and should accelerate the reaction. The experiments which confirm the radiation hypothesis

can be explained in this way. The observations of Lewis and Taylor (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 665) in case of decomposition of triethyl sulphonium bromide in various solvents, of Moran and Lewis (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 2286), for cane sugar inversion which support the radiation hypothesis, are characteristic reactions in which the active state and energy retention state are identical.

The author's conclusions are also interesting in the sense, that it gives a physical significance to the important modification of radiation hypothesis, by Dhar ("Chemical action of Light," 1931, p. 334; Gopal Rao and Dhar, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 646) that the frequency ν calculated from the temperature coefficient should be regarded as 'threshold frequency'; that is the minimum frequency that can accelerate the reaction. Dhar gives no sound justification for this statement. It may now be pointed out that the identity between active state and the energy retention state of Planck, is a limiting case by itself, or in the limit $E = Nh\nu$ and hence the frequency ν , so obtained denotes the threshold frequency which can start the chemical change, provided the two states are identified. Thus Dhar's view follows as a necessary consequence.

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